

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL POLITICS AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN THE MANAGEMENT PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: *This study explored the relationship between Organizational Politics (OP) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (organizational citizenship behavior for organization (OCB-O) and organizational citizenship behavior for individuals (OCB-I)). Survey data was gathered from 290 employees work in manufacturing company in Chonburi province. PLS-SEM was used to test the research hypotheses. Results revealed that OP has a negative relationship with OCB-O and OCB-I. Based on these findings, this study recommends that the manufacturing company in Chonburi province should eliminate or reduce OP practices as much as possible in their organizations. The limitations of this study and recommendations for future research are also provided.*

Key words: OCB-I, OCB-O, OP, manufacturing company

1. Introduction

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is one of the contemporary concepts that has strengthened interest in it during the last two decades, because of this concept of a prominent impact on the level of employee performance. The success of organizations today depends on the enthusiasm of their employees to achieve performance levels that exceed the set goals and objectives (Bashabesha & Hrahesha, 2011). OCB is a term that includes anything positive that employees do, any organization will get benefits from encouraging employees to engage in OCB to increase the efficiency, citizens satisfaction and reduce the costs of absenteeism. Therefore, the organizations should promote OCB in the workplace through employees' motivation, as well as creating workplace environment that support the OCB (Al Mahasneh, 2015). OCB has gained the attention of many organizations (Tong et al., 2015) and for the organizations to operate

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successfully, their employees must be prepared to do more than the minimum formal and specific aspect of their job functions (Nica et al., 2016).

Mouzelis (2017) suggested that OCBs directed to individuals (OCBI) and those directed to the organization (OCBO) should be distinguished. OCBO is a direct function of what employees think about their work characteristics. In contrast, OCBI is helping individuals at work, seems to have only indirect implications, for maintaining balance in the organization employee transaction (Landells & Erin, 2017; Mansbridge, 2018).

The manufacturing company in Chonburi province, which suffers from the absence of clear goals and central of in decision-making and the consequent failure to meet the needs of its employees, is in dire need to instill OCB among its employees. Because of its positive effects on the performance and reputation of public sector organizations, including improving performance, raising the morale of workers, and increase their job satisfaction, and reflected in the manner of dealing with citizens (Bashabesha & Hrahesha, 2011). Albloush et al. (2020) pointed out that OCB is very important in manufacturing company, which are part of public sector to enhance and increase job performance, and the municipal should instil OCB among employees, to increase their performance and provide the best services to citizens (Salomonsen, 2016).

Most people will agree that workplace politics is a reality of organizational life. Despite a wealth of studies regarding the separate effect of organizational politics (OP) on organizational outcomes, few have actually focused on the relationship between an individual's perceptions of organizational politics and his attempt to employ impression management behavior (Zia et al., 2017). According to the expectancy theory, individuals modify their behavior based on their calculation of anticipated outcomes (Onyango, 2017). Politics is an epidemic phenomenon in organizations and deserve more attentions and testing (Pereira et al., 2015). OP often interferes with organizations process (promotions and rewards) and damage organization productivity and employees performance (Purba et al., 2015). The nature of OP in the public sector has also received attention, arguing that there are higher levels of politics in this sector compared to the private sector (Vigoda & Kapun, 2005) and OP has a negative impact on public confidence in government and on the performance of public agencies (Purba et al., 2015).

Previous studies focus on the impact or the relationship between OP, Job performance and job satisfaction. As well as, prior studies were conduct in Some Asian countries, USA, and some Europe countries. Few studies and no recent studies conduct in Asia countries link between OP and OCB. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to explore the relationship between OP, OCBO and OCBI among employees in manufacturing company in Chonburi province.

2. Literature Review

2.1. *Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)*

OCB in the institution is receiving much attention from scholars (Eatough et al., 2011). The concept of OCB dates back to research by Katz (1964), who argued that organizations could increase their performance by relying on voluntary employee behaviors not prescribed by top management. Likewise, Schminke et al. (2015) envisioned OCB as a behavior above a role that cannot be imposed on employees and that stems from feelings of reciprocity. Thus, OCB reflects, “individual behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal rewards system and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization” (Organ, 1988). Although the OCB expands formal employee job definitions and is not directly compensated, it can make a significant contribution to employees and organizational effectiveness (Salomonsen, 2016).

Organ (1988) introduced OCB when he revisited the traditional concept of job performance. Organ noted that besides the quantitative aspects of the job, job performance was more than just a call of duty, and it included some qualitative aspects that he called the OCB that add to the social and psychological context of work (Atta & Khan, 2016). OCB is a great importance to the organization and the individual alike. The importance of this behavior stems from the fact that it contributes to improving the overall performance of the organization, by building a base of reciprocal relationships between employees in different departments. Also this behavior contributes to reducing the need to allocate the rare resources to maintenance jobs, and improve the ability of managers and co-workers to do their work, by allocating more time for effective planning, scheduling of work, and problem solving (Shrestha et al., 2015).

Previous studies identified several dimensions of OCB. Organ (1988) identifies the dimensions of altruism, conscientiousness, courtesy, sportsmanship, and civic virtue. Borman & Motowidlo (1993), conceive of OCB in terms of the extra effort and enthusiasm that employees undertake in work tasks; voluntary involvement in tasks that fall outside the prescribed task set; an extension of help to and cooperation with other organizational members; and the support, and defense of organizational objectives. Moreover, Purba et al., (2015) distinguish between citizenship behaviors that are directed toward the organization (OCBO) and toward the individuals (OCBI).

OCBO includes “behaviors that benefit the organization (e.g., gives advance notice when unable to come to work),” whereas OCBI includes “behaviors that immediately benefit specific

individuals (e.g., helps others who have been absent) (Landells, 2017). The significance of impact and perception may depend on whether OCBI or OCBO is under consideration. Assume that OCB is a deliberate attempt to maintain a balance in social exchange between employees and the organization, it is reasonable to suggest that this behavior is directly aimed at benefiting the organization (Lee & Allen, 2002). Thus, OCBO is likely to be a direct function of what employees think about their work characteristics. In contrast, OCBI, which primarily involves helping individuals at work, appears to have indirect effects, at best, of maintaining equilibrium in the organization employee relations (Lee & Allen, 2002).

OCBO is more closely related to employee beliefs than OCBI. Lam et al, (2016) showed that employee job perception, such as rewards and recognition, was associated with OCBO but not with OCBI. As well as, Bouckennooghe et al, (2014) state that fairness perceptions were more strongly related to OCBO than to OCBI. Consequently it seems reasonable to suggest that OCBO are more cognition-driven than affect-driven. In contrast, OCBI might have a stronger affective, than cognitive, underpinning (Lee & Allen, 2002).

2.2. Organizational politics (OP)

Politics is ubiquitous and is one of the most important phenomena in organizations (Pfeffer, 1992; Mintzberg, 1983). OP is a very complex phenomenon and its effects on organizational outcomes such as performance, job satisfaction and commitment are not easy to estimate (Vigoda, 2007). Bruning (2013) define OP as a behavior for influencing decision making, many others describe OP in terms of a self-serving behavior in organizations (Naseer et.al, 2019). Pereira et al. (2015) and Ferris (1989) similarly define OP as “a social influence process in which behavior is strategically designed to maximize short-term or long-term self interest, which is either consistent with or at the expense of others’ interest”.

Politics in the workplace, its nature, antecedent, and impact on work outcomes has become a stimulating field of study for the management scientist. OP is often considered dysfunctional to an organization because it has the potential to disrupt the organization’s efficiency and effectiveness. A workplace that is widespread with politics is stressful to work in, is not conducive for promoting positive job attitudes, and is likely to have a high employee turnover (Schminke et al, 2015). Vigoda (2007) stated that OP can be more destructive for public administration than for private organizations. The importance of OP lies in its potential consequences and its effect on work outcomes (Vigoda, 2007). Thus, politics often interferes with the normal organizational processes such as promotions and rewards (Vigoda, 2007).

The organizational politics construct has been investigated from a number of different approaches and at various levels of analysis. Prior research has focused on two main areas. One area that researchers have empirically examined is employees' perceptions of organizational politics (POP) while the other area is political behaviors. POP were suggested by Wang (2013) as a good measure of the general political atmosphere in organizations and an important dimension of individuals' perception of their work environment. Individuals react to the situation and behavior based on these perceptions (Muhammadet et al, 2018).

Cropanzano, Howes, Grandy, and Toth (1997) suggested that, for many individuals, organizational politics are perceived as a threat to their wellbeing and result in a variety of negative affective reactions such as increased job anxiety and reduced job satisfaction (Kacmar & Baron, 1999). Ferris, Russ, and Fandt (1989), pointed out that, POP are influenced by organizational factors, work environment factors, and personal factors, which, in turn, influence individual and organizational outcomes such as organizational withdrawal, job anxiety, job involvement, and job satisfaction. For employees who perceive high levels of organizational politics and feel that they have little control over these organizational processes, organizational politics likely would be perceived as a threat (Ferris et al., 1989). However, if employees feel that they have control over organizational processes, organizational politics will be perceived as an opportunity to promote their self-interests. POP have been researched extensively and have been shown to be related to antecedents (personal factors, situational factors) and important outcomes (psychological outcomes, attitudinal outcomes, and behavioral outcomes). Organizational politics perceptions have been found to be related to a negative work outcome such as decreased job involvement, reduced job satisfaction, increased intent to turnover and anxiety (Cropanzano et al., 1997) and reduced satisfaction with supervisor (Ferris et al., 1996).

On the other hand, political behavior, according to Ferris et al. (1989) is a no sanctioned behavior (deviate from norms) which may be harmful to the organizational goals or to the interests of others in the organization and which may be assumed self-serving in nature. political behavior is "the exercise of tactical influence by individuals which is strategically goal directed, rational conscious and intended to promote self- interest, either at the expense of or in support of others interests" (Valle & Perrewe, 2000).

2.3. Link between OP and OCB

When employees are convinced that organizational decision-making is characterized by strong self-service behaviors, they experience high levels of anxiety, as they fear that these behaviors may harm their ability to fulfill their job responsibilities (Crawford et al., 2010). This

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should reduce the likelihood that they will undertake activities that are not part of the official job description (Chang et al., 2012). In addition to limiting their ability to engage in OCB, OP should undermine motivations to engage in such behaviors. Employees who believe that self-service situations dominate organizational decision-making are likely to feel frustrated or even angry (Kacmar & Ferris, 1991), undermining their happiness with their jobs and their career status in general (Chang et al., 2009; Ferris & Kacmar, 1992). Moreover, social exchange theory indicates that when the employees view the organization as positive and favorable, the employees try to reciprocate with positive responses. Likewise, when employees perceive the organization as unfavorable to them, they react by increasing the unfavorable responses or decreasing the positive responses towards the organization (Khan et al, 2019).

It has often been observed that OP hinders the development process of organization by increasing the likelihood of negative work attitudes and behaviors (Atta & Khan, 2016). As well as, there is a strong relationship between OP and OCB in a sense that increase in OP resulted in a decrease in OCB (Vigoda, 2007). Atta and Khan (2016) use sample 494 from different public universities in Pakistan, the results show that OP negatively affect OCB. Similarity, data from a Mexican manufacturing organization reveal that OP reduces OCB (De Clercq & Belausteguigoitia, 2017). Moreover, Yongxing et al (2019) using a sample of 107 supervisor-subordinate dyads in China to examine the moderating effect of OP on the relationships between work engagement, in-role performance and OCBO. The results show that work engagement negatively related to supervisor-rated in-role performance and OCBO when the organizational is perceived as highly political. Khan & Gul (2018) applies social exchange theory to explain how the OP affects OCB. The study uses a sample of 392 supervisor-subordinate dyads from touring companies in Southern China. The results show that, OP negatively predicted OCB via moral efficacy. Therefore, we develop our hypothesis as follows:

Hypothesis 1: There is a negative relationship between OP and OCBO

Hypothesis 2: There is a negative relationship between OP and OCBI

Based on the literature review and hypotheses developed, this study presents a research framework as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Framework

3. Data and Methodology

The target population of this study comprised employees who in manufacturing company in Chonburi province. The researcher design questionnaire to collect data, 290 respond received. The respondents' profiles are depicted in Table 1. It appears that majority of respondents are male (90.7%). The results also show that, majority of the respondents are between 29 to 39 years old (44.5%), qualified with Bachelor's degree (36.6%), and with work experience of at least 5 to 15 years (46.2%).

Table 1: Profile of respondents (N=290)

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	263	90.7
	Female	27	9.3
Age	19-28	10	3.4
	29-39	129	44.5
	40-50	100	34.5
	> 50	51	17.6
Working Experience	5 <	52	17.9
	5-15	134	46.2
	16-26	76	26.2
	> 27	28	9.7
Education Level	High School or Less	71	24.4
	Diploma	104	35.9
	Bachelor's degree	106	36.6
	Master degree	9	3.1

The instruments used in this study were adopted from prior literature. Seven items to measure OCB-O and seven items to measure OCB-I adapted from lee and Allen (2002), thirteen items adapted from Kacmar and Carlson’s (1997) measured organizational politics. The instrument was based on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Measurement Model Results

The current study employed structural equation modelling (SEM) to evaluate the conceptual model and to test the hypotheses. The measurement model was test through the convergent validity and discriminant validity. To assess the convergent validity, results of the factor loadings, composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) were inspected (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2014). Items having a loading of more than 0.50 are acceptable for analysis (Hair et al., 2010), AVE of at least a value of 0.5, and CR having a value exceeding 0.7, are to be retained (Hair et al, 2010). Table 2 shows that all the latent constructs in this study have achieved convergent validity since the factor loadings are between 0.563 to 0.835, the CR values are above 0.80 and the AVE values are more than 0.50.

Table 2: Items Loading, AVE and Composite Reliability for the Measurement Model

Constructs	Items	Items loading	CR	AVE
Organizational politics (OP)	OP1	0.80	0.95	0.60
	OP2	0.81		
	OP3	0.76		
	OP4	0.80		
	OP5	0.80		
	OP6	0.83		
	OP7	0.81		
	OP8	0.71		
	OP9	0.73		
	OP10	0.76		
	OP11	0.74		
	OP12	0.74		
	OP13	0.78		
OCB-O	OCBO-1	0.79	0.89	0.54
	OCBO-2	0.80		
	OCBO-3	0.82		
	OCBO-4	0.65		
	OCBO-5	0.69		

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	OCBO-6	0.71		
	OCBO-7	0.64		
OCB-I	OCBI-1	0.69	0.87	0.51
	OCBI-2	0.80		
	OCBI-3	0.68		
	OCBI-4	0.80		
	OCBI-5	0.83		
	OCBI-6	0.58		
	OCBI-7	0.56		

Discriminant validity was used to test the measurement model. The criterion and cross-loading scores of Fornell and Larcker (1981) were used to establish discriminant validity. Table 3 demonstrates that the square root of AVE for all latent variables was higher than inter-construct correlations, confirming validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 3: Discriminant Validity Analysis

	OCB-I	OCB-O	OP
OCB-I	0.715		
OCB-O	0.534	0.735	
OP	-0.341	-0.434	0.780

4.2 Structural Model Results

This study utilized a PLS algorithm and standard bootstrapping procedures to examine path coefficients significance (Hair et al., 2014). Table 4 show path coefficient values and bootstrapping results for hypothesized relationships between study variables. Figure 2 illustrates the research model conceptualized in this study. As shown, R^2 values for OCB-O and OCB-I were 0.189 and 0.116 respectively, suggesting that 18.9% of the variance in OCB-O and 11.6% of the variance in OCB-I can be explained by OP.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

As indicated in Table 4, OP had a negative relationship with OCB-O and OCB-I ($\beta = -0.434$; $t = 5.522$; $p < 0.001$; $\beta = -0.341$; $t = 4.437$; $p < 0.001$). As a result, H1 and H2 was supported. According to these findings, manufacturing company employees working in an environment rife with OP, but who prefer the security of manufacturing company, will respond to such an environment by displaying apathy towards their work and neglecting their jobs, which negatively impacts their behavior (OCB-O and OCB-I). The current study highlighted that OP caused negative emotions and cognitions that affected employee behavior. Employees of manufacturing company that worked in an environment where OP was prevalent had feelings of injustice and

inequity, thus leading to lack of good behavior. When employees perceived that people relied on political acts to achieve their personal objectives, they were highly demotivated and showed dislike their work and do not appear extra role behavior or OCB. This observation is in line with prior result (Atta & Khan, 2016; Clercq & Belausteguioitia, 2017; Vigoda, 2007).

Table 4: Hypotheses Testing

Path	Hypothesis	Path Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Decision
OP → OCB-O	H1	-0.434	5.522	0.000	Supported
OP → OCB-I	H2	-0.341	4.437	0.000	Supported

5. Conclusion

This study has examined the relationship between OP, OCB-O and OCB-I. From this study's results the following conclusions can be made on the relationship between OP and OCB (OCB-O and OCB-I) among manufacturing company in Chonburi province. There was a negative relationship between OP and OCB. Accordingly, high degrees of OP reduced and weak employee behavior. Therefore, top management should ensure that formal policies and rules are appropriate for employees. Moreover, this study showed that the employee behavior of manufacturing company were weakened by OP practices. The findings of this study also offer practical implications. Based on the results, it is suggested that the managers or decision makers of manufacturing company in Thailand make an effort to reduce or eliminate the OP practice in their respective organizations. This study is important as the majority of studies related to OP and OCB (OCB-O and OCB-I).

6. Limitations and suggestions for future research

1. This study has offered some good insights into the issue of OP and OCB in the context of manufacturing company. Nonetheless, like all studies, it also faced several limitations. This study incorporated employees from few organizations. Second, the relationship between OP and OCB may be conceptualized as indirect, indicating a possible presence of some mediators and moderator, therefore this study recommend to use a mediator or moderator variable between OP and OCB, such as fairness or rewards.

2. This study was conducted using a quantitative study design based on the review of related literature and research studies in order to develop a research instrument. Data were

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collected and analyzed according to the concept of quantitative research. Future research should be conducted on the basis of a qualitative study design through an in-depth interview or group discussion so as to obtain in-depth data for developing organization

2. Spatial restriction in this study was the sample. The sample was selected within Chonburi province. For future research, the structural equation model developed from this research should be applied to the sample living outside Chonburi province so as to be useful for public and private organization

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